

Characterization Methods and Types of Electrical Noise in Resistors and Resistive Networks: A Systematic Review Protocol

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Protocol Registration

This systematic review protocol has been registered on **Zenodo**. The registration will be publicly accessible at [10.5281/zenodo.17162639](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17162639), which provides a permanent identifier (DOI) for this review.

Title Characterization Methods and Types of Electrical Noise in Resistors and Resistive Networks: A Systematic Review Protocol

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Rationale Electrical noise in resistors and resistive networks is a fundamental aspect of electrical measurements, instrumentation, and metrology. Although thermal and flicker noise are well known, the literature on characterization methods and their application to different resistor technologies is scattered. This review aims to systematically map resistor noise types, characterization approaches, and resistor technologies investigated.

Review Question *What types of electrical noise are present in resistors and resistive networks, and how are these noises characterized?*

Eligibility Criteria

- Inclusion: studies addressing electrical noise in resistors or resistive networks; reporting methods of noise characterization; peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, or preprints; English language.
- Exclusion: studies without characterization methods; studies focused on unrelated components; non-English publications.

Information Sources IEEE Xplore, Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, and Scispace. Last search date: 3 March 2025.

Search Strategy Keywords included: resistor, resistive network, electrical noise, thermal noise, flicker noise, 1/f noise, excess noise, shot noise, burst noise, characterization, measurement. Full search strategies will be made available as supplementary material.

Study Selection Two reviewers will screen titles and abstracts independently using Rayyan. Full texts will be assessed independently. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or a third reviewer.

Data Items Primary: noise type (thermal, flicker/1/f, shot, burst, excess), characterization method, resistor technology. Secondary: frequency range, temperature, instrumentation, sample size, environment.

Synthesis Qualitative synthesis (mapping noise types, methods, and resistor technologies) and descriptive quantitative analysis (frequencies and cross-tabulations). No meta-analysis of noise values will be performed due to heterogeneity.

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Conflicts of Interest The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability All search strategies, extracted datasets, and supplementary materials will be made publicly available on Zenodo.